

Coordinated MIMO with Single-fed Load-Controlled Parasitic Antenna Arrays

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Abstract

In this work, we present a method that enables the application of robust, low-complexity, arbitrary channel-aware precoding at single-fed load-controlled parasitic antenna arrays. Moreover, we describe the extension of this technique to multi-cell setups. Finally, we evaluate the sum-rate throughput performance of several multi-cell precoding schemes through numerical simulations based on realistic radiation patterns generated by antenna design software as well as on a scattering environment model. The results of the simulations confirm the expected performance gains over conventional single-fed configurations.

Index Terms

Coordinated multiple-input multiple-output (Co-MIMO), channel state information (CSI), inter-cell interference (ICI), load-controlled parasitic antenna array (LC-PAA), signal-to-interference-plus-noise-ratio (SINR).

I. INTRODUCTION

In view of the spectrum scarcity, multi-user multiple-input multiple-output (MU-MIMO) technology has been adopted in recent years by cellular mobile radio communications systems as a response to the enormous traffic growth. In the cellular downlink (DL), MU-MIMO leverages the spatial degrees-of-freedom (DoF) provided by multi-antenna base stations (BS) to enable the spatial multiplexing (SM) of data streams addressed to individual users, so that the spectral efficiency (SE) of the corresponding cells is increased, irrespective of the number of antennas at the user terminals (UT). Channel state information should be available at the transmitter (CSIT), for the mitigation of the multi-user interference (MUI) that arises due to the parallel co-channel transmissions to be possible with the help of appropriate precoding techniques. Then, the average capacity of the resulting MIMO broadcast channel (BC) grows with the number of service antennas, provided that there are at least as many users as transmit antennas [1].

Since both CSI and user data are available at the BS, the resulting MUI can be predicted in advance. Dirty paper coding (DPC) is a capacity-achieving multi-user encoding scheme that takes advantage of the non-causal knowledge of the MUI to subtract it prior to transmission [2]. However, the successive encodings and decodings involved in DPC turn this non-linear pre-processing method practically infeasible, especially when the number of users is large [2].

Linear precoding constitutes a suboptimal alternative that offers a good tradeoff between performance and complexity. This technique leverages the physical separation of the users to enable the spatial sharing of the channel through the application of transmit beamforming (BF). This communication paradigm is known as space-division multiple access (SDMA). The objectives in linear precoding are to (1) increase the signal power at the intended users and (2) reduce the interference at other users. However, the determination of the optimal BF vectors that meet these goals is a challenging task in most applications of practical interest (e.g., the maximisation of the sum-rate (SR) throughput) [3]. Hence, heuristic schemes are typically used.

Maximum ratio transmission (MRT) achieves goal (1): it utilises BF vectors that match to the intended users' channel vectors, thus maximising the signal power at these users. MRT is asymptotically optimal at the power-limited low signal-to-noise-ratio (SNR) regime, where typically time-division multiple access (TDMA) is employed (i.e., a single user is scheduled at each timeslot), since in this case the power gain attributed to the application of transmit BF is translated into a linear capacity gain [1]. However, its capacity floors at the DoF-limited high-SNR regime where SDMA is applied, since it cannot handle the intra-cell co-channel interference (CCI) [3].

Zero-forcing (ZF) precoding accomplishes goal (2): it makes use of BF vectors that are orthogonal to the subspace of other users' channel vectors in order to eliminate the MUI. In other words, the precoding matrix in this case is the pseudo-inverse of the multi-user channel matrix. Since the effective user channel vectors are orthogonalised, the capacity scaling of this technique depends on the employed user selection and power allocation (PA) schemes. ZF precoding attains a significant portion of the DPC capacity at the high SNR regime, especially when single-antenna terminals are utilised [2]. Also, it approaches the capacity as the number of users grows towards infinity, since in this case user selection benefits from the abundance of spatial directions and the multi-user diversity effect (i.e., nearly orthogonal users with high channel gains can be scheduled) [2]. On the other hand, ZF precoding is power-inefficient and, thus, performs poorly at low SNR [2].

Regularised ZF (RZF) precoding combines the advantages of these two extremes. It regularises the pseudo-inverse of the composite channel matrix by introducing a factor that controls the amount of the residual MUI that is allowed at the cell. The value of this coefficient is typically set such that the signal-to-interference-plus-noise-ratio (SINR) at the users is maximised.

Then, the capacity of this precoding scheme grows with the number of service antennas. RZF precoding is asymptotically optimal at low/high SNR and performs reasonably well at intermediate SNR [3].

Modern cellular systems utilise universal frequency reuse to increase the overall SE. In this case, co-channel transmissions from adjacent cells lead to inter-cell interference (ICI) which limits the system-wide capacity and degrades the cell-edge quality-of-service (QoS). Coordinated MIMO (Co-MIMO) is a recently emerged multi-cell extension of MU-MIMO that relies on the cooperation between neighbouring BSs to manage the ICI. BS cooperation involves the exchange of control information (e.g., user scheduling, power allocation, beamforming vectors / precoding matrices etc.), CSI, or / and user data over backhaul / fronthaul links. The various levels of cooperation differ on their backhaul / fronthaul capacity and latency requirements as well as on their performance gains over non-cooperative MIMO [4].

In general, the performance of coordinated MIMO benefits from an increase in the number of the antennas that are installed at the BSs, since in that case the SM and interference mitigation capabilities of these nodes are enhanced. Unfortunately, the hardware cost and power consumption grows with the number of antennas, since each active antenna element should be fed by a radio frequency (RF) chain, while the electromagnetic coupling that arises among closely spaced antennas reduces the radiation efficiency [1].

Load-controlled parasitic antenna arrays (LC-PAA) constitute an alternative technology that exploits the mutual coupling among the antennas to reduce the number of required RF modules for given spatial DoFs and allow smaller form factors [1]. In this paradigm, a limited number of active antennas is surrounded by passive antennas. The inter-element spacing is deliberately chosen to be tight, so that the feeding voltages of the active elements to induce currents at the so-called parasitic antennas, thus enabling them to participate in the formation of the radiation pattern. The parasitic elements are terminated to analogue loads. By adjusting the impedance of the parasitic loads, we can vary the amplitude and phase of the currents that run on the parasitic elements as desired.

LC-PAA can admit any input signal format in transmit BF applications, since the desired radiation beam pattern does not depend on the input data. In addition, in [1] and [5] has been shown that both open- and closed-loop MIMO transmission is possible, even with single-fed LC-PAA. However, in general, LC-PAA cannot admit any given input signal constellation or precoding scheme in closed-loop MIMO, because the required loading values, which determine the currents on the parasitic elements (which, in turn, depend on the precoded data), may result in negative input resistance which leads to circuit instability. In [6] is proposed the transmission of data signals that approximate the actual signals as a workaround to this problem. Nevertheless, the need to compute dynamically the optimal loading values constitutes a prohibitive factor for the commercial use of this antenna array technology.

In this paper, we describe a simpler and more robust channel-aware precoding approach that exploits the transmit BF capabilities of single-fed LC-PAA. Moreover, we extend this method to multi-cell setups. Several multi-cell precoding variants are evaluated through numerical simulations and the performance of the system is compared against equivalent setups that utilise single-RF antennas. The generalisation of this work to multi-active multi-passive (MAMP) configurations is straightforward.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows: Section II introduces the arbitrary channel-aware precoding framework. Section III describes the extension of this technique to multi-cell setups. Section IV presents the simulation results. Finally, Section V concludes the paper and presents future research directions.

Notation: a , \mathbf{a} , and \mathbf{A} denote a scalar, vector, and matrix. \mathbb{R} and \mathbb{C} denote the set of real and complex numbers. $\text{Re}\{\cdot\}$ denotes the real part of a complex-valued quantity. $|\cdot|$ denotes the magnitude (absolute value) of a complex-valued (real-valued) scalar. A_{ij} represents the element of \mathbf{A} at the i th row and j th column, while a_i denotes the i th entry of \mathbf{a} . $(\cdot)^T$, $(\cdot)^\dagger$, $(\cdot)^{-1}$, $(\cdot)^+$, $\text{tr}(\cdot)$, and $\text{diag}(\cdot)$ denote the transpose, Hermitian transpose, inverse, Moore-Penrose pseudo-inverse, trace, and diagonal of a matrix, respectively, while $\|\cdot\|$ stands for the Euclidean norm of a vector. \mathbf{I}_n and $\mathbf{0}_n$ denote the $n \times n$ identity and zero matrix. $\mathbb{C}^{n \times n}$ represents a $n \times n$ matrix with complex-valued entries. $\mathbb{E}(\cdot)$ denotes expectation, $\mathcal{CN}(\mu, \sigma^2)$ represents a complex-valued random variable (RV) that follows the Gaussian distribution and has mean value μ and variance σ^2 , and $\mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{M}, \sigma^2 \mathbf{I}_n)$ represents a complex-valued Gaussian vector whose mean value matrix is \mathbf{M} and its covariance matrix is $\sigma^2 \mathbf{I}_n$.

II. ARBITRARY CHANNEL-AWARE PRECODING

Fig. 1 shows the equivalent circuit diagram of a M -element single-fed LC-PAA whose $(M - 1)$ parasitic elements are connected to tuneable loads with purely imaginary impedance (e.g., varactor diodes). The relation between the currents and voltages associated with the antenna elements is given by the generalised Ohm's law as [5]

$$\mathbf{i} = (\mathbf{Z} + \mathbf{Z}_L)^{-1} \mathbf{v}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{i} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times 1}$ is the vector of the currents that run on the antenna elements; $\mathbf{Z} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times M}$ is the mutual coupling matrix whose diagonal entry $Z_{mm} \in \mathbb{C}$ represents the self-impedance of the m th antenna element while the off-diagonal entry $Z_{mk} \in \mathbb{C}$ denotes the mutual impedance between the m th and the k th antenna element ($m, k = 1, 2, \dots, M$); $\mathbf{Z}_L \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times M}$ is the diagonal load matrix whose diagonal elements are the source resistance $R_s \in \mathbb{R}$ and the impedances of the parasitic loads

Fig. 1. Equivalent circuit diagram of a single-fed load-controlled parasitic antenna array.

$jX_m \in \mathbb{C}$ ($m = 2, 3, \dots, M$), with $j = \sqrt{-1}$ denoting the imaginary unit; and $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times 1}$ is the voltage vector that holds the sole feeding voltage $v_s \in \mathbb{C}$.

The system model of a (M, N) MIMO link established between a transmitter (TX) and a receiver (RX) having M and N antennas, respectively, is given from an antenna perspective by [5]

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{i} + \mathbf{n}, \quad (2)$$

irrespective of the antenna array technology utilised at each end of the link. In Eq. (2), $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ is the vector of open-circuit voltages at the receive antennas, $\mathbf{i} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times 1}$ represents the vector of currents that run on the transmit antennas, $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$ denotes the channel matrix whose entry $h_{nm} \in \mathbb{C}$ relates the m th input current with the n th output open-circuit voltage ($m = 1, 2, \dots, M$; $n = 1, 2, \dots, N$), and $\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ constitutes a zero-mean circularly symmetric complex Gaussian (ZMCSCG) additive noise vector with covariance matrix $\mathbf{Q}_n = \mathbb{E}(\mathbf{n}\mathbf{n}^\dagger) = \sigma_n^2 \mathbf{I}_N$, i.e., $\mathbf{n} \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}_N, \sigma_n^2 \mathbf{I}_N)$. Note that the same relation holds also for the case where the N receive antennas are shared by K users.

Assuming the application of channel-aware precoding, the input-output signal relationship in Eq. (2) becomes

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{W}\mathbf{s} + \mathbf{n}, \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times M}$ is the precoding matrix and $\mathbf{s} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times 1}$ is the input signal vector.

Hence, in order to apply channel-aware precoding to a single-fed LC-PAA, we have to map the precoded symbols to the antenna currents as follows [5]:

$$\mathbf{i} = \mathbf{W}\mathbf{s}. \quad (4)$$

After calculating the required currents for the desired precoding scheme and the given input signal format according to Eq. (4), we should compute the corresponding loading values according to Eq. (1) under the constraint of a positive input resistance, i.e., $\text{Re}\{Z_{in}\} > 0$, in order to ensure that the antenna system will not reflect power back [7]. The value of the input resistance depends on the impedances of the loads, which are determined by the antenna currents. The latter, in turn, depend on the precoded signals. Hence, it becomes apparent that this design condition cannot be met for any given input signal constellation or precoding scheme.

On the other hand, single-fed LC-PAAAs can admit any input signal in transmit BF applications, since the array manifold required to shape the radiation pattern as desired does not depend on the format of the input signal. The role of the parasitic loads in this case is to generate currents with appropriate magnitude and phase shift, so that the desired beam is produced. This is similar with the functionality of BF weights in conventional antenna arrays. The only condition that has to be met is that the loadings should be tuned within a range of reasonable values.

Based on this remark, we suggest a novel approach for performing *robust, low-complexity, arbitrary channel-aware precoding* with single-fed LC-PAAAs: (1) First, we apply transmit BF using any valid method. (2) Then, we perform channel-aware precoding over the employed beam.

By taking advantage of the radiation pattern reconfiguration capabilities of single-fed LC-PAAAs through the decoupling of the problem to a BF and a precoding part, we overcome the circuit stability and implementation complexity issues. Complexity can be further reduced if instead of using tuneable loads and adjusting their impedance with the help of a control circuit, we utilise various sets of fixed loadings and switch between the different loading configurations.

Fig. 2. System model for $K = 2$ and $L = 4$.

III. MULTI-CELL PRECODING

In this section, we present the system and signal models for the considered multi-cell setup and precoding techniques as well as the corresponding transmission protocol.

A. System Setup and Transmission Protocol

We consider the DL transmission in a setup with K cells and one active user per cell. At each timeslot, each BS wishes to serve its scheduled user. The K transmissions take place over the same frequency band. Each BS is equipped with a single-fed LC-PAA with M antenna elements, while the users utilise single-antenna terminals. The BSs can efficiently share control information (e.g., SINR values) or I and CSI over high-speed backhaul / fronthaul links, while the UTs perform non-cooperative single-user decoding¹. Each single-fed LC-PAA is able to generate L distinct predetermined beams that correspond to L fixed sets of loading values. Hence, there are L^K possible beam combinations (K -tuples of beams) in total. We assume a flat- and block-fading channel model, a frequency division duplex (FDD) operation mode, and unit-variance noise (i.e., $\sigma_n^2 = 1$).

The system operation is divided in three phases:

- 1) **Learning phase:** For each beam combination, the BSs transmit a pilot signal. Then, the UTs either measure their SINR or estimate the channel gains related with the cross and direct links and feed back to their BS these channel quality metrics.
- 2) **Beam-selection phase:** Based on the information reported by the UTs, the BSs select jointly the best K -tuple of beams in terms of the achieved SR throughput (one beam per LC-PAA is selected).
- 3) **Transmission phase:** The BSs transmit over the selected beams. Either non-precoding-based or precoding-based transmission takes place.

The system setup is shown in Fig. 2 for $K = 2$ and $L = 4$.

¹The considered set of cells represents a cooperation cluster in realistic multi-cell setups. The cluster formation and user scheduling problems are beyond the scope of this paper. Moreover, perfect CSIT is assumed.

B. Channel Quality Metrics and Beam-Selection Criteria

Let us assume that the UTs measure during the learning phase their SINR for each beam combination (l), where $l = 1, 2, \dots, L^K$. Since $\sigma_n^2 = 1$, the SINR at UT $_k$ is given by

$$\text{SINR}_k^{(l)} = \frac{\left| h_{kk}^{(l)} \right|^2 p_k}{\sum_{m \neq k} \left| h_{km}^{(l)} \right|^2 p_m + 1}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, K \quad (5)$$

where $h_{kk}^{(l)}, h_{km}^{(l)} \in \mathbb{C}$ is the channel from BS $_k$ and BS $_m$ to UT $_k$, respectively², while $p_k, p_m \in \mathbb{R}$ is the transmit power of these BSs. Note that in the learning phase, each BS transmits using full power P (it is assumed to be the same for all BSs).

Then, the UTs calculate their data rate as

$$R_k^{(l)} = \log_2 \left(1 + \text{SINR}_k^{(l)} \right) \quad (6)$$

and report it back to their BS. The BSs exchange these real values and calculate the corresponding SR throughput as

$$R^{(l)} = \sum_{k=1}^K R_k^{(l)} = \sum_{k=1}^K \log_2 \left(1 + \text{SINR}_k^{(l)} \right). \quad (7)$$

Now, let us assume that each terminal UT $_k$ estimates the direct channel with BS $_k$ and the cross channels with the other BSs $h_{kk}^{(l)} \in \mathbb{C}$ and $h_{km}^{(l)} \in \mathbb{C}$, respectively, for each beam combination (l) during the learning phase and feeds them back to its BS.

Then, the BSs exchange these complex values and compile the composite channel matrix $\mathbf{H}^{(l)} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{h}_1^{(l)} & \mathbf{h}_2^{(l)} & \dots & \mathbf{h}_K^{(l)} \end{bmatrix}^\dagger \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times K}$ where $\mathbf{h}_k^{(l)} \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times 1}$ is the vector of the channel coefficients between UT $_k$ and each BS $h_{km}^{(l)} \in \mathbb{C}$ ($m = 1, 2, \dots, K$).

Next, the metric $T^{(l)} = \text{tr} \left(\mathbf{H}^{(l)} \left(\mathbf{H}^{(l)} \right)^\dagger \right)^{-1}$ is calculated.

After switching through all possible beam combinations, the BSs select jointly the optimum beam combination according to one of the following rules, depending on the type of channel quality metric reported back to the BSs by the UTs:

- **SINR-based beam selection criterion:** The K -tuple of beams (l) that results in the maximum SR throughput $R^{(l)}$ is selected.
- **CSI-based beam selection criterion:** The K -tuple of beams (l) that results in the minimum value of $T^{(l)}$ is selected.

C. System Model

Initially, we consider non-precoding-based DL transmission over the selected beam combination. The symbol-sampled complex-baseband received signal $y_k \in \mathbb{C}$ at UT $_k$ is given by³

$$y_k = \sqrt{p_m} \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger \mathbf{s} + n_k, \quad k, m = 1, 2, \dots, K \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{s} = [s_1 \ s_2 \ \dots \ s_K]^T \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times 1}$ is the symbol vector, with $s_m \in \mathbb{C}$ being the data symbol intended for UT $_m$, and $n_k \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$ is the additive noise.

We can represent Eq. (8) in a more compact form as

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{H} \mathbf{P}^{1/2} \mathbf{s} + \mathbf{n}, \quad (9)$$

where $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times 1}$ is the vector of the received signals, $\mathbf{P} = \text{diag}(\sqrt{p_1}, \sqrt{p_2}, \dots, \sqrt{p_K}) \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times K}$ is the PA matrix, and $\mathbf{n} \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}_K, \mathbf{I}_K) \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times 1}$ is the ZMCSCG additive noise vector.

Denoting $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{P}^{1/2} \mathbf{s}$, we obtain

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{H} \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{n}. \quad (10)$$

In precoding-based transmission, on the other hand, we have $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{W} \mathbf{P}^{1/2} \mathbf{s}$, where $\mathbf{W} = [\mathbf{w}_1 \ \mathbf{w}_2 \ \dots \ \mathbf{w}_K] \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times K}$ is the precoding matrix and $\mathbf{w}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times 1}$ is the BF vector used to transmit s_k to UT $_k$. Hence, Eq. (9) becomes

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{H} \mathbf{W} \mathbf{P}^{1/2} \mathbf{s} + \mathbf{n}. \quad (11)$$

In other words,

$$y_k = \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger \left(\sum_{m=1}^K \mathbf{w}_m \sqrt{p_m} s_m \right) + n_k, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, K. \quad (12)$$

²Note that each BS-UT link is actually a single-input single-output (SISO) channel.

³Note that, for notational convenience, we have omitted the beam combination index as well as the dependence of the received signal on the path loss and shadowing effects. The latter is assumed that are absorbed in the variance of the composite channel matrix elements.

Note that in this case, the SINR at UT_k is expressed as

$$\text{SINR}_k = \frac{\left| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger \mathbf{w}_k \right|^2 p_k}{\sum_{m \neq k} \left| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger \mathbf{w}_m \right|^2 p_m + 1}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, K. \quad (13)$$

D. Multi-cell Precoding

We consider three precoding variants. In MRT,

$$\mathbf{v}_k^{(\text{MRT})} = \mathbf{h}_k, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, K. \quad (14a)$$

$$\mathbf{w}_k^{(\text{MRT})} = \frac{\mathbf{v}_k^{(\text{MRT})}}{\left\| \mathbf{v}_k^{(\text{MRT})} \right\|}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, K. \quad (14b)$$

Note that the BF vector is normalised, as it is the common practice.

In ZF precoding, MUI (or ICI in the considered setup) is nulled, i.e.,

$$\left\| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger \mathbf{w}_m^{(\text{ZF})} \right\|^2 = 0, \quad k, m = 1, 2, \dots, K, \quad m \neq k. \quad (15)$$

Hence, the received signal of the k th user can be expressed as

$$y_k = \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger \sqrt{p_k} \mathbf{w}_k^{(\text{ZF})} s_k + n_k, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, K. \quad (16)$$

In view of Eq. (15), the SINR at the k th user is given by

$$\text{SINR}_k^{(\text{ZF})} = \left\| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger \mathbf{w}_k^{(\text{ZF})} \right\|^2 p_k, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, K. \quad (17)$$

The ZF condition is translated into the use of the Moore-Penrose pseudo-inverse of the composite channel matrix as the precoding matrix:

$$\mathbf{F}^{(\text{ZF})} = \mathbf{H}^+ = \mathbf{H}^\dagger (\mathbf{H}\mathbf{H}^\dagger)^{-1}. \quad (18a)$$

$$\mathbf{W}^{(\text{ZF})} = \frac{\mathbf{F}^{(\text{ZF})}(:, k)}{\left\| \mathbf{F}^{(\text{ZF})}(:, k) \right\|}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, K. \quad (18b)$$

Finally, in RZF precoding we have

$$\mathbf{v}_k^{(\text{RZF})} = \mathbf{H}^\dagger \left(\frac{1}{p_k} \mathbf{I}_K + \mathbf{H}\mathbf{H}^\dagger \right)^{-1}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, K. \quad (19a)$$

$$\mathbf{w}_k^{(\text{RZF})} = \frac{\mathbf{v}_k^{(\text{RZF})}}{\left\| \mathbf{v}_k^{(\text{RZF})} \right\|}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, K. \quad (19b)$$

IV. NUMERICAL SIMULATION RESULTS

In this Section, we evaluate the performance of the considered system setup for the use case that is depicted in Fig. 2 through numerical simulations over target receive SNR values in the range $[-20, 30]$ dB. We consider (a) non-precoding-based transmission, where the beam pair selection is based on SINR feedback; (b) ZF precoding, where the beam pair selection is based on SINR feedback; (c) MRT, ZF, and RZF precoding where the beam pair selection is based on CSI feedback; and (d) ZF precoding in an equivalent single-RF setup where each BS is equipped with a single omni-directional antenna instead of a LC-PAA. We make the realistic assumption of per-BS power constraints $p_k \leq P$, where $P \in \mathbb{R}$ is the maximum attainable transmit power (same for all BSs). The water-filling (WF) PA scheme described in ([3], Eq. (3.37)) is applied. The performance results represent ergodic SR throughput obtained after 1,000 simulation runs by taking the expectation of the corresponding SR equations. Also, a single-bounce scattering model has been incorporated in the simulations to capture both the effects of beamforming-based transmission as well as of small-scale and large-scale fading. The beams have been calculated with the help of appropriate antenna design software. They have a half-power beam width (HPBW) of 30° and correspond to a single-fed LC-PAA with $M = 5$ elements. Finally, the channel matrix has been normalized appropriately to facilitate the performance evaluation.

Some interesting remarks can be made based on Fig. 3.

- The average SR throughput of non-precoding-based transmission and MRT floors at high SNR due to the residual ICI.
- ZF precoding with LC-PAA outperforms its omni-antenna counterpart over the entire SNR range, even when the beam pair selection is based on SINR feedback, due to the power gain attributed to transmit BF.

Fig. 3. Numerical simulation results: Average SR throughput.

- Beam pair selection based on CSI feedback improves significantly the performance of ZF precoding, since in this case the beam pair selection and precoding tasks are performed jointly.
- Non-precoding-based transmission outperforms ZF precoding with omni-antennas over the entire range of relevant SNRs (i.e., until the SR throughput flooring at the high SNR regime occurs)! In fact, non-precoding-based transmission almost resembles MRT. Hence, we note that *we can significantly reduce complexity and still pay only a negligible penalty on performance*.
- Finally, we note that MRT is optimal at low SNR, ZF with beam pair selection based on CSI feedback is optimal at high SNR, and RZF approaches these two extremes at the corresponding SNR regimes while it performs better at intermediate SNRs, as expected.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we described a novel approach that enables us to perform robust, low-complexity, arbitrary multi-cell precoding with single-fed LC-PAA. Numerical simulation results based on realistic beam patterns confirmed the performance gains of this approach over equivalent single-RF setups. In the future, we plan to extend this work to MAMP configurations and setups with multiple users per cell.

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